

AN IMPORTANT SOURCE FOR STUDYING OF THE POLITICAL HISTORY OF THE BUKHARA KHANATES IN THE SIXTH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The founder of Manghit dynasty, Muhammad Rahim (1747–1758), the leading Manghit offspring in Bukhara brought into being his own dynasty and took the government control in his hands, and the politics of creating powerful and centralized governments continues under the reign of emir Shohmurod (1785 – 1800), and emir Nasrulloh (1827–1860) . The Emirate held its position as the biggest country in Central Asia even at the first half of the XIXth century.

The founder of Manghit dynasty, Muhammad Rahim (1747–1758), the leading Manghit offspring in Bukhara brought into being his own dynasty and took the government control in his hands, and the politics of creating powerful and centralized governments continues under the reign of emir Shohmurod (1785 – 1800), and emir Nasrulloh (1827–1860) . The Emirate held its position as the biggest country in Central Asia even at the first half of the XIXth century. At that period the territories of Bukharan emirate comprised today's Zarafshon valley, the oasis of Samarqand, oasis of Kashkadaryo, and oasis of Surkhandaryo, the cities and villages in the valley of the rivers Vakhsh, Kofirnihon and Pandj, oasis of Murgob, also the cities such as: Dushanbe, Regar, Kurgontepa and other inclusive regions. Territories: Chordju (at present Turkmenbashi), Kerki and for certain period Marv (not far from Mari town) were included. Also, Balkh town, northern territory along Amudarya in Afganistan (Shibirgon, Toshqorgon, Ahcha, Andhuy, Mozori Sharif and others), Balkh region remained under the power of Bukharan rulers till 1850. This article reviews some of the manuscript dating back to XIXth century concerning history of Central Asian Khanates' political relations during the reign of emir Sayed Nasrulloh in XIXth century. Manuscript has not previously been studied by Uzbek or other foreign scholars. The anonymous author cites facts reliably and accurately narrates historical events relating to the relationship of Bukharan emirate with Kokand khanate. It can be assumed that he was a direct participant in emir Nasrulloh's trips to Kokand Khanate. Translation of Professor I. Rakhmatova, indicates that information on the book of victories related to areas of the Kokand Khanate, to which a significant portion of work is devoted, more comprehensive and profound information about other areas is described by author. There is some inaccurate and sometimes erroneous data found in reports on events outside the Kokand

Khanate. This is especially true of the relationship between Bukhara and Khiva's kingdoms and the events of the first Anglo-Afghan war etc. All this is explained by the fact that the author himself was not an eyewitness of these events, but this information was acquired from secondary or tertiary sources. It should be noted that Bukharian historiography disagree and partly contradict the question of succession of emir Nasrulloh. According to the "Zafarnomayi khusrawi" emir Khaidar died on 4 rabi al-awwal 1242 H / 6 October 1826 . He left six sons: Mir Muhammad Khusayn Khan, Sayid emir Nasrulloh, emir Umar Khan, emir Zabir Khan, emir Khamza Khan, emir Safdar Khan. As is evident from the list, only emir Nasrulloh used the title "Sayid" as a symbol of his noble descent (his mother a descendant of Juyebar khodja). The author indicates that of all the sons, only Nasrulloh is higher-ranked and more noble than others. At that time, eldest son emir Khaidar, emir Khussain was in Bukhara, and emir Nasrulloh was in Karshi , Umar Khan in Karmine region, and others, while still young's, were in Bukhara. The author wrote that the emir's eldest son mirzo Khussain was in the makhalla Bozorkhoja in the city of Bukhara and he was under house arrest. The official historian of emir Nasrulloh tries to make a version by writing about the virtues of his patron in order to be elected king; he also introduces the idea of the legality of his claim to power. Ahmad Danish, Mirza Shams Bukhari have written that mirzo Khussain was a worthy person for the throne of Manghit dynasty. Unfortunately, from the beginning mirzo Khussain could not find support amongst high dignitaries of the court. A senior government official in Bukhara, Muhammad Hakim qushbegi , who played an important role in emir Khaidar's administration and he knew well mirzo Khussain, began intrigue against the legitimate heir. He thought that he (qushbegi) will lose power during mirzo Khussain's administration. Therefore he found it more profitable for himself and his command to support emir Khaidar's other son, mirzo Nasrulloh (born 16 jumada al-awwal 1221/1 June 1806, died 19 rabi 'II 1277/19 October 1860) . Mirzo Khussain held in Bukhara, emirate's throne 75 days and died. We think that in his death qushbegi played a big role. Qushbegi sent a secret letter to emir Nasrulloh, the second son of emir Khaidar and successor prince after mirzo Khusaen but the proponents of mirzo Khussain sent letter to next successor Mirzo Umar in Karmine, proposing accession to the throne. Mirzo Umar Khan comes closer to the capital (Bukhara) and tries to occupy the Bukharan throne. Nasrulloh had known about the event but he remained in Karshi. Therefore, the death of mirzo Khussain and the question of succession split the Bukharan castle into two camps. Supporters of mirzo Umar Khan were headed by Ismatulloh bie, Tagai khan, Abdurasul pansadbashi . Supporters of Nasrulloh were led by Muhammad Hakim qushbegi, Rajab beg and Dunmas dodkho etc. following an unsuccessful attempt to bring on the throne of his successor, qushbegi, fearing public opposition from the supporters of Umar Khan, was forced to declare Umar as Emir. But mirzo Umar could hold Bukhara's throne only four months and six days. The period of emir Umar had been described very negatively in the chronicle. The author writes that Umar could not run the country and was not interested in affairs of state. The population was subjected to all sorts of harassment, high taxes; and residents of the capital were brought to an extreme degree of devastation. The dignitaries of the throne created the opposition in order to overthrow emir Umar. Qushbegi was in contact with mirzo Nasrulloh and sent a messenger inviting Nasrulloh to reach the capital. After gathering a huge army emir Nasrulloh, after 50 days siege of Bukhara citadel, and "20 days of the month shaban 1242/20 (Hijra), March, 1827", with the active support of Khakim qushbegi, Rajabbek

divanbegi, and Ayaz biyathe city gates of Bukhara were opened. Emir Nasrulloh finally occupied the throne. The anonymous author of "Zafarnomayi Khusrawi" dates of the Emir's entrance to the capital as 27 ramadan 1242/24, April 1827. Sadr Ziya also indicates that emir Nasrulloh sat on the throne on thursday, in ramadan 1242 / April 23, 1827. Therefore, the author of "Zafarnomayi Khusrawi" and "Montakhab of al-Taworikh", cite evidence, with some discrepancies, of occupation throne by emir Nasrulloh. The month shaban and ramadan 1242 H /March-April, 1827 year. In this case it will be possible to eliminate the mistakes made by many previous authors in determining the reign of emir Nasrulloh and his predecessors Mir Khussain and Mir Umar. After success in Bukhara, emir Nasrulloh sent his younger brother Khamza to Narazim, a former district of Bukhara along the reaches of Amu-darya (Amu River). Nasrulloh sent there Safdar tyura who was second brother of Khamza. In "Zafarnomayi Khusrawi", it is clearly stated that "on the advice of well-wishers to prevent unforeseen circumstances," the princes were exiled to Narazim and "forever imprisoned". According to Muhammad Hakim Khan, soon emir Nasrulloh requested Mirahur Gazibek qalmyk to kill three princes, which was granted. Among those killed were 17 people from among the servants and family members of the emir. Young emir Nasrulloh began a desperate struggle for strengthening of the central government. Nasrulloh punished ruthlessly supporters of emir Umar, who fled and lived in Herat, and later moved to Kokand. Married to the daughter of Mahmud ibn Daniyal bie atalik, emir Khaidar's uncle lived there for three years and died of the plague in 1244/1828-29 r). To create powerful support in his regime, Emir Nasrulloh accepted a compromise. He appointed authority representatives and leaders of tribal chiefs, and representatives of clergy and local dignitaries to high posts. At the same time, he had to wage a fierce battle against local rulers and leaders of the rebellious tribes in order to strengthen his power and to subordinate new territories. A special problem, he created the rulers Shakhrisabz, also, population Miyankala, Jizzak, Yam, Zaamin, Ura-Tube and Khujand which was bordered with Kokand khanate. Emir also led troops to the northern Afghanistan. Emir Nasrulloh, after another carefully prepared 32 expeditions in 1271/1856 Shakhrisabz, took possession of Kitab and took prisoner bek Shakhrisabz Iskandar dodkhoh along with his family and entourage. Being married to the daughter of the ruler on behalf of Kenegas tribe. "Zafarnomayi Khusrawi" provides important information on the history of relations between emir Nasrulloh and Kokand state. In this regard, special place is occupied by military campaigns of emir Nasrulloh against the Kokand ruler Muhamad Ali Khan (Madalikhan, 1822-1842). Emir Nasrulloh, in his reign, made more than a dozen military trips to the Jizzakh, Yam, Zaamin and Uratube districts and undertook four devastating campaign against Kokand Khanate from 1840 to 1842. It should be noted that conquering aspirations of emir Bukhara in the last 40 years of XIXth century, can explain the capture of Kokand Khanate and punishment of Madali Khan, reason cited as turning away of Madali Khan from the true faith. The reason for expeditions of emir Nasrulloh in Kokand were mentioned briefly: Kokand governor, emir Umar Khan, at the end of his reign, married daughter of a native of Uratube region khodja Sayyid Ghazi, known as Khonposhsho. After the death of Umar Khan, the said widow married son of Umar Khan, Madali khan. With the help and participation of opponents of Madali Khan, especially Mukhammad Khakim Khan, author of "Muntakhab al-Tavorikh", suspects the news of this marriage to "my mother" reached emir Nasrulloh. Muhammad Khakim Khan scion of Kokand Khans (nephew of Umar Khan, son of his sister and

Masumkhan tura) was afraid of being expelled from the Kokand khanate by Madali Khan. Mukhammad Khakim Khan wrote to emir Nasrulloh several times and offered to punish the apostate (Madali Khan) who had married his own mother. Thus, under the pretext of establishing "Sharia", emir took the opportunity and led his troops to conquer Kokand. At first invasion emir Nasrulloh took Kokand with strengthened Peshogar, but accepted Kokand Khanate's proposal and concluded peace. After return to Samarkand, he held a council and told military commanders and dignitaries that he doubted the durability of this peace and friendship. Emir Nasrulloh was invited to call on Madali Khan's younger brother, Sultan Mahmud Khan, who had been expelled by his brother from the khanate and lived in Shakhrisabz. After arrival, Nasrulloh appointed Sultan Mahmud governor of Urmetana, in a possession located at the top of the Zarafshan river. Emir Nasrulloh used Sultan Mahmud as a worthy candidate to the throne of Kokand, but it caused anger and resentment in Madali Khan. After the departure of emir of Bukhara, Madali Khan invited his brother, Sultan Mahmud to get the region of Tashkent and Dasht Kipchak. He agreed to turn away from emir and went to Tashkent. Madali Khan also added some land of Bukhara to his possessions. The third campaign by emir Nasrulloh was carried out in the spring of 1842. The author of "Zafarnomayi Khusrawi" gave a very detailed description of the course and consequences of this campaign. Emir expressed in this campaign unprecedented cruelty. He executed 5,000 people from Kokand, robbed and destroyed homes in many towns and villages. The capital of khanate was looted. In Margelan town of Madali Khan and his brother Sultan Mahmud fled but were captured and executed by Nasrulloh's army on their way to Tashkent. Madali Khan's son Muhammad Amin Khan, his mother, poetess Nadira, were also amongst the killed. Two women of Madali Khan's harem, Khonposhsha, - the fatal woman, according to Mukhammad Khakim Khan, were sent to Bukhara. For two months she lived in the harem of emir Nasrulloh. Emir not believing her honesty, finally gave the order to kill her with two offspring, born from his marriage to Madali Khan. According to the works of Bukhara and Kokand's historiography, the fourth campaign in Kokand emir Nasrulloh made after, the revolt of Kokand against emir's mayor Ibrakhim paravanachi. Revolt was joined with Kirghiz-kipchaks tribes under Sherali-khan 4 jumada al-akhir 1258/13 July 1842. Campaign of emir Nasrulloh has caused a huge impact on governance of Kokand. The already weak central government reeled under the blows of internecine wars, not only amongst nomadic tribes of the valley, but also as a result of opposition to the settled and nomadic population. As a result of emir's expeditions, the process of confrontation grew Bukhara invaded the political arena in Kokand, Kirghiz and Kipchak tribes, the new political and military elements, played a destabilizing and a centrifugal role in the history of Kokand khanate and its elimination. It later caused the Russian conquest of Muslim Central Asian territories too.

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46. Zafarnama-yi Khusrawi (facsimile) - C.36.

47. Mirahur-head of horse-holder in emirate. one of the important post in Bukhara emirate . See: Muhammadhakimhon. Muntahab al-Taworikh. - P.44.

48. Muhammad Hakimkhon. Muntahab al-Tavorih. - P. 43. There is evidence that he was poisoned. They were executed as soon Hakim kushbegi, Ayazby and Ismatulla, those who helped him in his studies of the throne of Bukhara.

49. Ancient city where was born Emir Temur in 1336. Today Shahrisabz is one of historical city in south of Uzbekistan.

50. Next big Uzbek tribes has fought against Mangits dynasty because Kenges considered Mangits has not legitimated khans(kings) in Bukhara throne. By traditional rule in Bukhara government should sit in throne Chingizids dynasty as legitimate Khans

